

ARDC Medical Research Data Integration Framework

“True integration is about creating a whole that is greater than the sum of its parts, where each element enhances the value of the others.”

– *Stephen Covey*

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Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge the traditional custodians throughout Australia and their continuing connection to, and deep knowledge of, the land and waters. We pay our respects to Elders both past and present.

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Executive Summary

In this document, the ARDC proposes a framework for the systematic integration and use of data from electronic medical records (EMRs) across Australia for research and analysis. At the core of this proposal is the adoption of the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM), an internationally recognised standard that can harmonise health data across different EMR and health care systems. By implementing the OMOP CDM, this framework aims to standardise EMR data, enhance interoperability, and support local, national, and international collaborative research projects. Such a capability would also provide significant internal analytics and business intelligence opportunities for health service providers and policymakers. We also advocate for the establishment of an **“Australian Health Data to Evidence Network”** to coordinate the adoption and implementation of the OMOP CDM across Australia, initially focused on EMR data. This document outlines key governance, security, and privacy considerations to ensure the framework’s successful integration into existing health data systems to create an enhanced infrastructure for health data research.

1. Introduction

The framework described in this document aims to support systematic, secure, and ethical access to electronic medical records data in Australia for the purposes of research and analysis.

The healthcare sector in Australia is a multibillion-dollar industry. In the 2021-22 financial year, Australia invested approximately \$241.3 billion in health goods and services. Healthcare spending has grown at an average annual rate of 3.4% over the past decade, now accounting for 10.5% of Australia's GDP¹. This significant investment is accompanied by the generation of millions of patients records each year. These records are vital not only for patient care but also as a valuable resource for research. Analysis of the data these records hold has informed the development of more effective health care practices, increased safety, efficiency, and equity in healthcare services, and substantial cost savings for the government.

A particularly important application is post-marketing surveillance of health technologies, such as medications and devices, to understand their use and outcomes.

However, the ability to harness this potential is limited by several challenges. There are significant governance, ethical, and practical barriers to accessing and using these records. There is a lack of harmony across the system with inconsistent formats and organisational structures across practices, hospitals, and health authorities. Patient records are often stored in fragmented repositories, making them difficult to manage and use due to inconsistent data terminology. Standardising these data would enable comparisons and foster innovation. This requires a significant investment of effort and time in developing data

infrastructure that can overcome the complex data access, ethics and governance issues to deliver reliable and high-quality evidence^{2 3}.

Common data models (CDMs) have been developed to address the need for data standardisation. A variety of CDMs have been developed, however, with the most widely adopted and most comprehensive is the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model. This public-private initiative, involving the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), pharmaceutical companies, and healthcare providers, was established to enhance the use of observational healthcare databases for research^{4,5}.

Along with the global adoption of the OMOP data model, an international “infrastructure” for using this observational data scientifically has emerged including:

- validated analytical software,
- informatics services,
- data science and statistical methodologies,
- training resources and communities of practice,
- processes for the generation and dissemination of clinical evidence.

This capability is coordinated by the Observational Health Data and Informatics initiative (OHDSI) with participation across 83 countries⁶.

The framework being outlined in this document proposes that Australia adopt and implement the OMOP Common Data Model, and related capability, to enable more effective leverage of existing hospital EMR databases. The translation of data to this CDM will facilitate distributed network analyses across individual hospital databases and across states who have different EMR systems and lay the foundation data-driven advancements in health care including AI.

Problem Statement

The healthcare research data landscape in Australia is highly fragmented, characterised by diverse data formats and inconsistent access to standardised datasets, and varying levels of analytical expertise. These challenges hinder collaboration, slow research progress, and limit the potential for discoveries that could lead to significant improvements in patient outcomes and health systems. Confined to small-scale, local analytics and research, Australia’s health system and innovation capability risks being left behind in a big data world.

Proposed Solution

To address this fragmentation, we propose the development and adoption of a harmonised, interoperable analytics framework underpinned by the OMOP Common Data Model. This framework will standardise data across institutions and advance governance mechanisms to facilitate seamless collaboration, and empower researchers, service providers and policymakers to apply advanced analytical tools to derive robust and more timely insights from these data. The OMOP Common Data Model is a world standard approach with over 544 datasets across the world already standardised to the format, in 54 countries, accounting for 12% of the world's population. By leveraging this approach, Australia can accelerate research, enhance patient outcomes, and position itself as a global leader in healthcare innovation through data-driven discoveries.

1.1. Value Proposition

1.1.1. National Collaboration for Data Standardisation

We propose collaborating with the OHDSI, to address the challenge of data standardisation across a network of hospital-based EMR data resources. The partnership would foster collaboration with a global community of researchers and data scientists to:

- 1. Standardise hospital based EMR data:** Implementing the OMOP Common Data Model. This will ensure uniformity and enable comparability of distributed network analyses across various institutions and jurisdictions.
- 2. Enable distributed research:** Enable a mechanism to deploy validated analytical tools to address diverse research questions critical in the Australian context and enhance Australian participation in global network research. Utilise open-source software to reduce financial burdens on institutions and researchers. Establish a research ready infrastructure capable of timely responses to global health emergencies, such as pandemics.
- 3. Develop research capacity:** Offer capacity building and training programs to perform data standardisation activities and enhance the analytical and research skills to take advantage of the developed research data infrastructure.
- 4. Enhance capability of health systems improvement:** Ensure data quality and timeliness. Support existing and future clinical quality registries to simplify and more efficiently access data and improve data integrity and reliability.
- 5. Alignment with Australian Policy:** Ensure the framework is strategically aligned with policy initiatives, including the digital health strategy and ongoing data infrastructure and access initiatives. This alignment will help ensure that harmonisation efforts within hospital EMR datasets can be effectively translated to other areas.

1.1.2. Potential Benefits of OMOP Common Data Model

Adopting the OMOP Common Data Model and leveraging the associated OHDSI international science infrastructure would lead to a number of benefits for:

Help health service data holders

- *Standardise data:* Implement the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) to ensure uniformity and comparability across studies and health systems.
- *Avoid siloing:* Enable data to participate seamlessly in local, national, and international analytics.
- *Improve security and privacy:* operational data is untouched; analytics data (without personal information) is locally governed; only queries and aggregate responses are exchanged externally.
- *Reduce impost on health data holders:* replace bespoke data supply with standard data queries, making it easier to contribute data for monitoring, analytics and research.

Help health service providers and policymakers

- *Improve baseline understanding* provide “business intelligence” on health service usage at local, state, and national levels to help decision making and planning.
- *Enable rapid response:* Establish a research ready infrastructure capable of timely responses to global health emergencies, such as pandemics.
- *Enable surveillance:* for low frequency, post marketing adverse events.
- *Enable monitoring:* of treatment efficacy or of the impact of regulatory decisions.

Help researchers and innovators

- *Generate evidence for positive impacts:* real world data generating reliable evidence to improve healthcare guidelines, therapeutics, diagnostics, devices and service operations.
- *Foster collaboration:* Unite with a global community of scientists to share knowledge, data, technical and intellectual resources.
- *Enhance research capabilities:* Provide a comprehensive catalogue of validated analytics tools to address diverse research needs.
- *Develop research talent:* Offer capacity building programs to enhance the analytical skills of researchers.
- *Facilitate global partnerships:* Promote international collaborations to amplify research impact.
- *Minimise research costs:* Utilise open-source software and streamline access to quality data to reduce financial burdens on institutions and researchers.

Sharing technology can lead to:

- *Increased efficiency:* reuse of analytics tools and software.

- *Improved transparency and reproducibility:* compare findings from different data sources with a variety of methods without sharing the actual data and protecting patient privacy.
- *Scalability:* conducting studies by leveraging the data from multiple locations and settings.

By addressing these barriers and offering these solutions, the consortium aims to provide a step change to healthcare research—accelerating scientific discoveries, improving patient care, and advancing global health.

1.2. Integrating Common Data Models for the Quadruple Aim

Key Insight

The **Quadruple Aim framework**⁷ is widely adopted across Australia's healthcare system to drive improvement in four key areas: patient experience, population health, cost efficiency, and healthcare provider wellbeing. National reforms, such as Australia's Primary Care 10 Year Plan and the NSW Health Strategic Framework for Integrating Care, apply this framework to guide actions and measure success.

The integration of common data models, such as OMOP, can play a pivotal role in advancing the Quadruple Aim by enhancing data interoperability, improving clinical decision making, and promoting a more efficient and patient-centred approach to care.

2. Overview of Common Data Models and FHIR

2.1. OMOP Common Data Model

The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM) is a system designed to standardise health data from various sources, enabling easy comparison and analysis.

Healthcare providers such as hospitals, clinics, and laboratories often use different systems to collect a patient's clinical information. This can result in data being stored in various formats, making it difficult to use together. The OMOP CDM addresses this challenge by converting all that information into a common structure, simplifying the process of sharing, analysing, and learning from the data. This standardisation ultimately helps to generate the evidence that can be used to improve healthcare treatments and policies.

The OMOP CDM provides a “lingua franca” common structure so that analytic questions can be shared and answered across multiple health services. In essence, the OMOP CDM turns complex, scattered health data into an organised and usable form, allowing for better decision-making in patient outcomes and public health.

The OMOP CDM is not a new medical terminology standard. It uses by default existing international terminologies and classifications such as SNOMED, ICD, and RXNorm but also supports extension to local or discipline specific terms.

While this document does not delve deeply into the technical aspects of OMOP CDM (as detailed information is readily available elsewhere), a brief overview of the transformation process is shown in Figure 1.

In practical terms, transforming medical data into the OMOP CDM is like translating different languages into a single common language. This makes the data easier to understand, compare, and analyse, regardless of its origin. Like any language conversion, there are complexities that are key areas the integration framework processes will address. The process ultimately enables researchers and healthcare professionals to use the data more effectively, driving improvements in patient care and public health outcomes.

Key Insight: Transformation Process

1. Data Mapping (Data Structure Harmonisation): The first step is mapping the medical data from different sources—such as hospitals, clinics, or labs—to the standard OMOP CDM format. This involves identifying how existing data elements (like patient demographics, diagnoses, medications, and laboratory results) in the source data correspond to the standardised tables and fields in the OMOP CDM.

2. Transformation: Once the data structure is mapped to the CDM, next the data elements are translated to a common standard vocabulary. For instance, a diagnosis code from a hospital's EMR system that is captured as an ICD10 code is converted into the standardised code used in OMOP CDM, a SNOWMED-CT code. This step helps ensure that data from different sources is compatible and consistent in identifying specific medical concepts.

3. Continuous Updating: As new data becomes available or original databases are updated, this process may need to be repeated to keep the CDM current. This ensures that the standardised dataset remains accurate and valuable for ongoing research and analysis.

Figure 1. Overview of OMOP CDM transformation process

2.1.1. Strength in Numbers: International Adoption of the OMOP Common Data Model

The OMOP CDM has rapidly gained global momentum, driven by the need for standardised health data to support large-scale research and healthcare improvements. Across Europe, initiatives like the European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN)⁸ lead the adoption of OMOP CDM, aiming to harmonise health data through a collaborative network. Supported by the Innovative Medicines Initiative, this effort involves extensive collaboration among multiple European countries—including Denmark, Italy, Spain, France, and the Netherlands—to map diverse health data sources to the OMOP CDM. This harmonisation enhances data interoperability across Europe and facilitates collaborative research. The EHDEN is an exemplar initiative which could be replicated in Australia across state and territory boundaries⁸.

A notable milestone in 2023 was the adoption of OMOP CDM by the NHS Research Secure Data Environment Network in the UK⁹. This move marked a significant step in standardising health data across the country, allowing for more efficient and consistent access to healthcare data for research, regardless of its source. The adoption maintains security at the source while enabling researchers to conduct analyses across multiple sources, enhancing the comparability and quality of their findings. By aligning with OHDSI, the UK's research network positions itself for more effective global collaboration, integrating UK data into international studies and contributing to advancements in healthcare research worldwide.

In the United States, OMOP CDM adoption is widespread and its implementation has enabled numerous large-scale observational studies^{10,11}. The model is widely used in federally funded research projects and by numerous healthcare organisations.

The open-source nature of OMOP CDM, coupled with its widespread adoption in both Europe and the U.S., underscores its value as a global standard for health data harmonisation. Countries in the Asia Pacific region¹² have also widely adopted OMOP CDM, further solidifying its status as an international standard.

Given these international successes, adopting OMOP CDM in Australia presents an opportunity to align with global best practices. This alignment would enhance research capabilities and support better health outcomes across our nation.

It should be noted that the full realisation of the advantages of the OMOP CDM does require record-linkage – the adoption of the OMOP CDM by the NHS Research Secure Data Environment Network in the UK being an example. Linkage is not a core part of this project however ensuring OMOP-converted datasets have the governance considerations to support it is.

2.2. Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources

FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources)¹³ is an approach to making healthcare information easier to share and understand across different systems. Think of it as a courier

service that helps different healthcare systems—like those used by doctors, hospitals, and laboratories—easily exchange health information. This means that patient data could be quickly accessed and used, no matter where the patient is being treated, leading to better, more coordinated care, fewer mistakes, and ultimately, improved health outcomes.

In simple terms, FHIR makes sure that the right information gets to the right place at the right time, helping doctors and other healthcare providers make better decisions for their patients.

The value of FHIR has long been recognised both internationally and in Australia. In 2023, Sparked, Australia’s first FHIR Accelerator was launched. The Sparked community includes government bodies, technology vendors, provider organisations, peak bodies, practitioners, and domain experts. Together, they aim to accelerate the creation and adoption of national FHIR standards for healthcare information exchange.

FHIR and OMOP CDM are both systems designed to improve healthcare data management, but they serve different purposes and complement each other.

In essence, FHIR facilitates the efficient exchange of health information in a patient care environment, while OMOP CDM is used to store collections of patient records to help in understanding and using that information for subsequent analytics, research, and policy making. Together, they ensure that healthcare data is not only shared effectively but also used to improve health outcomes and inform decisions at higher levels.

2.2.1. FHIR and OMOP CDM: Bridging Patient Care and Big Data Analytics

FHIR facilitates real-time, patient-centric data exchange, making it essential for clinical settings, while OMOP CDM enables group-level analytics across healthcare institutions, making it ideal for research and population health analysis. A full comparison of FHIR and OMOP CDM is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of FHIR and OMOP CDM

	FHIR	OMOP CDM
Focus	FHIR is designed for real-time data exchange with a focus on individual patient care. It enables seamless communication between systems for clinical workflows, supporting direct care decisions, patient records, and rapid access to health information. FHIR resources are modular and tailored for fine-grained, specific tasks such as patient data, diagnostics, and treatments. As a file transfer format,	OMOP CDM is geared toward analytics on a large scale. It standardises and harmonises clinical data across institutions to support observational research, large-scale health analytics, and outcomes studies. OMOP CDM is primarily used to aggregate data for longitudinal research, epidemiology, and healthcare system performance evaluation. OMOP data is persistent.

	FHIR data can be transitory i.e. not persistent.	
Data Usage	FHIR is used in scenarios requiring real-time, point-of-care information exchange. This could include sharing patient records, laboratory results, or medication details between healthcare providers and systems.	OMOP CDM is used for retrospective research and analysis. It is ideal for creating cohorts, identifying trends, and understanding the effects of interventions across large populations.
Data Structure	FHIR employs a resource-based architecture, with each piece of data (such as patient information, medication orders, or laboratory results) treated as a "resource" that can be queried individually. It is designed to be highly flexible for different health systems and care settings.	OMOP CDM is a relational data model designed for research purposes. It structures data into tables representing clinical events, observations, medications, procedures, and more, allowing researchers to analyse and compare data across multiple sources in a consistent way.
Interoperability	FHIR is a key standard in the modern interoperability space, facilitating integration between electronic medical record (EMR) systems, mobile apps, and other healthcare tools. FHIR is a standard that EMRs can speak.	OMOP CDM standardises data from different sources into a common format, ensuring that researchers can apply consistent methods across datasets from different institutions. OMOP is a standard that analytic tools can speak.
Use Cases	FHIR supports clinical workflows, electronic health record systems, patient portals, and mobile health apps. It is used in situations where up-to-date patient information is needed quickly.	OMOP CDM is more suited for research applications, including clinical trials, drug safety monitoring, and observational studies, where data analysis across a large cohort is key.

2.2.2. Real Time Integration with FHIR

Australia’s prior investment in digital health, including state-wide EMR rollouts and FHIR based interoperability, has set up a solid foundation for a rollout of OMOP CDM. Using FHIR, data from EMRs could be mapped and transferred to OMOP CDM databases in an automated fashion, enabling continuous and timely updates. This real-time integration would help ensure that the OMOP CDM data remains current with the latest clinical

information. Recognising the potential of this approach, Health Level Seven International (HL7) and OHDSI have announced a collaboration to improve data sharing and tracking across FHIR and OMOP CDM data models¹⁴. Although still in its early stages, this initiative holds significant promise for enhancing interoperability and supporting more efficient healthcare research. As the integration framework progresses, it will need to consider governance mechanisms to enable any proposal to undertake FHIR to OMOP automation.

3. Health Data in Australia

The storage of health data in Australia is fragmented and inconsistent. While some states implemented state-wide for public sector tertiary care health data, others follow a more informal approach. Private tertiary hospital systems have varying penetration of EMR but contribute discharge coded data to government. Primary care health data is largely managed by individual general practices or networks. Private specialist practices have varying penetration of EMR systems that are generally different to both hospital-based EMR and GP systems. Consequently, conducting research on this data, despite its potential value, has traditionally been challenging and limited to isolated datasets.

Health data in Australia is stored in various locations, however four principal locations are:

- 1. Electronic Medical Records (EMRs):** The focus of this framework. Healthcare providers, including hospitals and clinics, maintain patient data in their own EMR systems, either on-site or via secure cloud solutions.
- 2. Disease Registries:** Australia has various national, state-based, and condition-specific registries that collect data on specific diseases or care systems and processes.
- 3. My Health Record¹⁵:** This national digital health record system, managed by the Australian Digital Health Agency, stores health information for individuals who have not opted out. It allows authorised healthcare providers to access patient data, improving continuity of care.
- 4. Administrative Data:** The Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), the Population Health Research Network (PHRN) and State Health Authorities hold extensive state and national level administrative data including national death data, Medical Benefits Schedule (MBS) and Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) data and hospital separations data. This data includes information on healthcare utilisation, costs, and health outcomes, which is essential for population health research and policymaking.

3.1. Electronic Medical Records

Electronic Medical Record (EMR) systems provide several benefits for clinicians. They enhance access to patient information, streamline workflows for clinicians, and improve communication among healthcare providers, leading to better clinical decision-making. By

reducing paperwork and minimising errors, EMRs increase the efficiency of healthcare delivery, allowing for quicker access to patient data and more timely diagnoses and treatments.

Beyond these benefits, EMR systems also hold significant potential for advancing medical research and improving patient outcomes. When appropriate de-identification process and governance processes are applied, the vast amount of data collected through EMRs can be analysed to uncover valuable insights into disease patterns, treatment efficacy, and population health trends. This could be particularly powerful when combined with artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies, which can process and interpret large datasets to identify correlations and patterns that might not be apparent through traditional research methods. However, it is important to emphasise that such secondary use of medical data must be governed by strict protocols and ethical guidelines to protect patient privacy and ensure data security.

In Australia, EMR adoption has historically been organic, with minimal central or state-level coordination. However, the landscape is now maturing, with states beginning to take a more holistic approach. Notably, Queensland has implemented a state-wide Oracle-Cerner Instance, and New South Wales is deploying a Single Digital Patient Record (SDPR) system based on the Epic EMR and South Australia has a single state-wide EMR system, Sunrise, based on the Allscripts platform.

3.2. Evidence Summary of Public Hospital EMR implementations across Australia

This summary provides a description of the implementation of Public EMR systems across all Australian states and territories. It highlights the variations in deployment and adoption within different regions, offering insights into the current landscape of digital healthcare infrastructure across the country. (More information is also available in Appendix 1)

New South Wales (NSW)

The state has chosen Epic as its platform for a statewide electronic medical record (EMR) system. A significant initiative is underway to develop a Single Digital Patient Record (SDPR) based on Epic¹⁶ and will replace many existing Cerner implementations over the next decade. Currently various local health districts use different systems; for instance, Sydney LHD uses Cerner⁵.

Queensland (QLD)

Implemented Cerner Millennium EMR system across 16 Hospital and Health Services⁵.

South Australia (SA)

Uses Sunrise (Allscripts) EMR across various health services.

Western Australia (WA)

Transitioned from BOSSnet to Allscripts Opal17 (rebranded in July 2021).

Integrated with the Sunrise EMR system in several emergency departments.

Victoria (VIC)

Decentralised EMR landscape with hospitals choosing their own platforms:

Epic: Used at Royal Melbourne Hospital, The Royal Children's Hospital Melbourne, Royal Women's and Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre⁵.

Cerner: Adopted by Austin Health, Northern Health, Eastern Health, Western Health, Monash Health and Peninsula Health.

Allscripts Sunrise: Deployed across multiple sites, including Gippsland Health Alliance.

Trakcare: Bendigo Health, South Western Area Health Service

Australian Capital Territory (ACT)

Implemented Epic Digital Health Record (DHR) system in 2022.

Largest Epic implementation in Asia Pacific, featuring 11 modules.

Conducting a pilot for 'DHR Link' portal, allowing GP access to patient records.

Northern Territory (NT)

Royal Darwin Hospital uses Alcidion's Miya Precision for patient journey management.

Recently implemented Acacia EMR system, built on InterSystems' TrakCare¹⁸.

Tasmania (TAS)

Currently uses the Tasmania Digital Medical Record (DMR), an older system.

The DMR is scheduled to be replaced, indicating a future transition to a more modern EMR system¹⁹.

Figure 2. Public Hospital Electronic Medical Records Systems in Australia

3.2.1. Current Landscape: Implementation of the OMOP Common Data Model in Australia

The OMOP CDM has been in use in Australia for the past six years, with in hospital EMRs across several states, including Queensland, New South Wales, and Victoria. One of the most extensive initiatives is the ongoing conversion of electronic medical records to the CDM in Queensland. Other significant datasets have been converted at institutions such as Austin Health, Western Health, and The Royal Children’s Hospital Melbourne in Victoria. Additionally, Sydney Local Health District (LHD) has integrated a substantial dataset into the OMOP CDM. This activity was coordinated by the University of Melbourne as part of the EMR to OMOP CDM project funded by the ARDC¹.

There are notable examples of substantial primary care datasets at the University of Melbourne and the University of New South Wales. These datasets hold significant potential for linking with hospital records, enabling the possibility of tracking the entire patient journey across different healthcare settings.

3.2.2. OMOP CDM Conversions in Primary Care EMRs and Administrative Datasets

Notable examples of primary care datasets converted to the OMOP CDM include those at the University of Melbourne and the University of New South Wales²⁰. Another example is

¹ <https://doi.org/10.47486/PS014>

the PBS 10% dataset—a standardised, longitudinal, unit-record extract containing a random 10% sample of PBS data in Australia.

Converting the initial tranche of data to the CDM requires a significant upfront investment. However, once the data is converted, maintaining it, and progressively refining and monitoring data quality, becomes relatively straightforward. This process does necessitate some human resources and an ongoing support model. Nevertheless, the return on investment justifies this relatively modest cost. Since the data holds significant research value, a collaborative funding model involving universities, research institutions, and other stakeholders would be beneficial to support the conversion, reflecting a shared investment in the shared benefits of enhanced data interoperability.

4. Governance, Security and Privacy

4.1. Governance for EMR Conversion into OMOP CDM Using Existing Structures

Key Principle

Effective governance is essential for the successful establishment of a research layer using EMR data based on the OMOP CDM. It is crucial to acknowledge that hospitals and states already have established data governance procedures. **The key principle is that the research layer should, wherever possible, build on these existing governance processes**, making adaptations only when necessary to meet specific requirements⁵.

This initiative is founded on the principle that local governance authorities and processes must determine who has access to the data and the methods of access. However, we anticipate several efficiencies that will emerge from the implementation of these new OMOP CDM data assets:

- They are being created with “research and analysis” as an approved category of purpose.
- Scientists from outside the data custodian organisations are an approved category of user.
- There will be ongoing research infrastructure support for the logistics of governance activities.
- Data request fulfilment will be greatly streamlined when the request comes in OMOP CDM format and the data custodians’ data is already in OMOP CDM.

The following implementation recommendations and guidelines serve as a best practice checklist for the nodes of the proposed initiative, while also recognising any existing local arrangements.

4.1.1. Leverage Existing Governance Structures

Steering Committee

Representation: A committee will be formed that has by integrating representatives from existing hospital governance boards, state health departments, research bodies, and patient advocacy groups. This ensures alignment of governance with current local frameworks while ensuring diverse input.

Responsibilities:

- Coordinate the statewide EMR conversion into OMOP CDM while leveraging existing hospital and state data governance mechanisms.
- Secure funding for project setup and ongoing support, while minimising disruption to existing governance workflows.
- Oversee project implementation using established reporting and accountability structures within hospitals and state health authorities.

4.1.2. Work within Current Data Governance Policies

Data Access and Usage

Build upon current hospital and state policies on data access, ensuring these align with OMOP CDM requirements. Define conditions for accessing OMOP CDM-converted data within the constraints of preexisting agreements and protocols.

Data Security and Privacy

Utilise existing security frameworks and privacy measures already in place within hospitals and states to safeguard patient data. Ensure compliance with Australian privacy laws by integrating existing de-identification and audit procedures into the OMOP CDM conversion process. Ensure the appropriate trusted environments and processes are available.

Data Quality Management

Adopt and if necessary, extend current hospital/state data quality checks by incorporating OMOP CDM-specific tools like the OHDSI Quality Dashboard and OHDSI Achilles. Integrate these into ongoing quality management efforts to ensure consistency and reliability.

Create additional quality assessment mechanisms to determine the completeness and quality of EMR conversions noting the OHDSI tools only assesses the quality/plausibility of the converted data.

Obtain and maintain standard data mappings and ETL code functions to evolve and standardise the quality of the converted data.

Consent and Ethics

Collaborate with ethics committees and consider existing consent models at the state or institutional level, distinguishing between requirements for research-specific consent and routine data analysis. Engage local ethics bodies to ensure that OMOP CDM usage aligns with ethical guidelines for both research and operational data handling.

Risk Mitigation

Strengthen existing risk management strategies in hospitals and states by adding OMOP CDM specific protocols for encryption, access control, and breach notification. Build on current monitoring and response procedures for managing data breaches.

Patient Perspective

Incorporating patient perspectives is essential for fostering trust and transparency in the secondary use of healthcare information for research. Achieving this requires developing strategies for clear communication with patients about the benefits of using their data within the OMOP CDM. It is important to address concerns related to data sharing, ensuring that patients understand and feel empowered about how their data will be used for research purposes. Engaging with patient advocacy groups, such as the Consumers Health Forum of Australia²¹, and including members of the public on data governance committees can further strengthen this approach by ensuring patient voices are heard and considered in decision making processes. Consumer participation in research committees enables consumer priorities to be addressed (e.g. Rare disease research)

4.1.3. Utilise Existing Technical Infrastructure

Data Mapping and Standardisation

Leverage hospital and state resources already involved in data management to standardise local EMR data elements for OMOP CDM. Build upon existing expertise with terminologies like SNOMED CT and LOINC.

Infrastructure and Technology

Where possible, adapt existing IT infrastructure and platforms within hospitals and states for hosting the OMOP CDM database. This ensures scalability and security while maximising existing interoperability efforts with local systems.

Data Conversion and Validation

Embed data conversion and validation processes into current hospital workflows, using automated tools and localised validation procedures to ensure smooth conversion into OMOP CDM.

4.1.4. Foster Collaboration and Data Sharing Using Existing Agreements

Data Sharing Agreement

Build on existing inter-institutional agreements to create an OMOP CDM-specific data sharing framework. Define ownership, access rights, and publication policies that align with current data sharing practices at the state and hospital levels.

Community Engagement

Continue leveraging current partnerships with the OHDSI community and other OMOP CDM adopters to foster collaboration and share best practices. Use existing channels for knowledge sharing for contributing to the OMOP CDM.

Promote Transparency and Trust

Communicate how OMOP CDM conversion fits into existing hospital and state data practices. Ensure the public and patients understand the added value of the OMOP CDM conversion while maintaining confidence in the data protection measures already in place.

4.1.5. Ensure Sustainability and Long-Term Support Through Existing Mechanisms

Secure Ongoing Funding

Work with existing hospital and state funding bodies to secure sustainable financial support for OMOP CDM conversion. Align these efforts with current budgeting processes to ensure the longevity of the platform.

Regular Reviews and Updates

Use established hospital/state review mechanisms to periodically evaluate and update data governance policies, technical infrastructure, and data quality procedures, ensuring they remain aligned with regulatory changes and technological advancements.

Training and Workforce Development

Leverage existing training programs for hospital data custodians, analysts, and researchers, enhancing them with OMOP CDM-specific guidance and tools to minimise disruption to ongoing operations. Expand workforce training initiatives in hospitals and state health departments to incorporate specialised OMOP CDM knowledge, ensuring staff are equipped with the necessary skills for data management, analysis, and interpretation within the OMOP CDM framework. As OMOP CDM adoption becomes more widespread, accessing relevant training resources will become easier, with extensive online support available through platforms like the EHDEN academy and vendor OMOP CDM offerings (see box below). It is important to emphasise that these skills complement existing expertise, such as database management and SQL proficiency, enabling a seamless transition and maximising the value of the workforce's current capabilities.

Key Insight: Vendor Support for OMOP CDM

Major vendors, including Microsoft²² and AWS²³, are advancing healthcare data capabilities by offering OMOP CDM support. Microsoft's integration of *OMOP analytics*²² into its healthcare data solutions on Microsoft Fabric represents a significant step, enabling healthcare organisations to standardise and analyse data more effectively. Similarly, AWS has developed resources to support OMOP CDM adoption, furthering opportunities for scalable, interoperable data management. Together, these offerings from leading cloud providers create a streamlined path for adopting the OMOP CDM in healthcare settings.

4.2. Data Security and Privacy for Statewide EMR Conversion into OMOP CDM

In the context of converting statewide EMRs into the OMOP CDM in Australia, ensuring data security and privacy is crucial. The following key aspects should be considered:

4.2.1. Leveraging Existing Security Protocols

Current Hospital and State Frameworks: Most hospitals and state health departments already have strong security protocols in place, including access controls, encryption, and auditing measures. For this initiative, it is essential to build on these existing systems rather than duplicating efforts.

Alignment with Australian Privacy Laws: Compliance with the Australian Privacy Principles (APPs) under the Privacy Act 1988 is mandatory. By working within existing hospital/state governance structures, the initiative can ensure adherence to these laws, including patient data confidentiality, proper storage, and secure transmission.

4.2.2. De-Identification and Data Privacy

A key requirement for using EMR data in research within the OMOP CDM framework is ensuring proper de-identification^{5,20}. Where possible, existing de-identification processes used by hospitals and state health departments should be leveraged. If enhancements or new methods are needed, there are readily available solutions that can be implemented. By building on current practices, this approach ensures compliance while minimising disruptions to established workflows.

Patient Privacy and Consent: Privacy protection is an important element of the initiative. While using existing hospital consent models (such as opt-out systems), it is important to engage with ethics committees to ensure that OMOP CDM aligns with the expectations of patients and complies with the National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) guidelines. Transparency about how patient data will be used, and the steps taken to protect it, is vital for maintaining public trust.

4.2.3. Data Access Control

Granular Role-Based Access: Given that OMOP CDM will likely be used by a diverse group of researchers and analysts, the initiative must implement a role-based access control system. This should be aligned with the access control mechanisms already in place at hospitals and within state health departments, ensuring that only authorised personnel can access sensitive information.

Audit Trails and Monitoring: Existing hospital and state health systems typically employ detailed audit trails to track who accesses patient data, when, and for what purpose. These audit trails should be extended to include OMOP CDM data access to maintain full transparency and accountability. This will also enable the early detection of any unauthorised access or potential data breaches.

In the above, it should be noted that OMOP provides mechanisms whereby a researcher can submit their question and receive results back without being granted access.

4.2.4. Risk Mitigation and Incident Response

Risk Management Frameworks: Hospitals and states already have comprehensive risk management frameworks in place to handle data breaches and other security incidents. For the OMOP CDM conversion, the initiative should integrate with these frameworks, extending them to include specific risks associated with large-scale EMR conversions, such as data corruption or misuse during the mapping process.

Existing security controls used in hospital IT infrastructure should be applied to the OMOP CDM converted data. Additionally, secure storage solutions need to be reviewed to ensure they meet both hospital/state security standards and OMOP CDM's research requirements.

5. Proposed Model of Implementation in Australia

This framework highlights the need to standardise research data across Australia through the adoption of the OMOP CDM. The key challenge remains: how can this be achieved effectively?

5.1. Evidence Network

The *Evidence Network* is a proposed national data infrastructure initiative aimed at supporting the generation of evidence to guide evidence-based health policy and services in Australia. It will aim to establish a framework for implementing common data models, governance, access, and analytics, particularly focusing on hospital EMR.

To initiate this transformation, we propose a three-year establishment project (2025-2028) under the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy, with ARDC co-investing in developmental activities.

5.2. Data Network

The following describe the activities of the framework to enable adoption of OMOP CDM for research data infrastructure.

5.2.1. Data Asset Development

Development of a set of new OMOP CDM data assets.

- *Data Conversion*: Developing Extraction, Transformation, and Loading (ETL) processes for converting EMRs into analysis-ready data assets.
- *Data Quality Assessment* – investigating the quality and completeness of data conversion including checking the extent to which original EMR data has contributed to the converted dataset
- *Data mapping and ETL sharing and standardisation* – ensuring we do not ‘re-invent the wheel’ with each data conversion and ensuring we do not permit data conversions that lock hospitals to a particular ETL provider / process.
- *Governance Policy*: Establishing robust frameworks to ensure data integrity and compliance.
- *Access Logistics and Procedures*: Streamlining data access while safeguarding privacy and security.
- *Business-as-Usual (BaU) Update Processes*: Creating sustainable mechanisms for regular updates, including investigation of FIHR-based automation¹⁴.
- *Research Access Business Model*: Facilitating research access to data.
- *Monitoring and Reporting Capability*: Implementing systems to track progress and outcomes.

5.2.2. Research Coordination

Coordinated network of researchers and analysts.

- *Coordination of Multi Centre Studies*: Facilitating collaborative research across institutions.
- *Research Methodology Training*: Enabling researcher to take advantage of the new data.
- *Common Analytics Processes*: Designing shared frameworks and automation tools.
- *Shared Tools, Coding, and Modelling*: Promoting collaboration through common resources.
- *Monitoring and Reporting Capability*: Implementing systems to track progress and outcomes.
- A publication and authorship policy

5.2.3. Capability Building

Learning how to participate in the new paradigm.

- Skills and resource programs to support:

- the establishment and maintenance of OMOP CDM data assets
- the governance, ethics and consent arrangements
- research teams build necessary skills, including informatics, statistics and data science.

5.2.4. Federation Services

- Central shared services such as:
 - Data discovery portal
 - Study and query automation tools and services
 - Data quality assessment tools and services

5.2.5. Digital health policy advocacy

- Data sharing arrangements including support for data linkage of OMOP datasets
- Ethics approval coherency
- Research infrastructure policy

5.2.6. Evidence Network Launch

The establishment project aims to launch the Evidence Network with:

- *Data Nodes*: Engaging at least four states, territory, or commonwealth agencies and local health service data holders.
- *Research Participation*: Involving stakeholders from the Group of Eight (Go8) universities and key Medical Research Institutes (MRIs).
- *Thought Leadership*: Collaborating with commonwealth and state digital health agencies, the research sector, and local health services.
- Support for individual OMOP CDM clinical sites to understand their own data for local audit and research.

5.2.7. Collaborative Entities

The project will partner with various stakeholders, including:

- OHDSI Australia as our connection to OHDSI International
- Commonwealth Agencies: Australian Digital Health Agency, Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), Safety Commission, Department of Health and Aged Care (DoHAC)
- State Health Departments
- Research Institutions
- Health Services
- Federation Services
- National EMR Data Discovery Initiatives
- Clinical Quality Registries
- GP data networks

By establishing a unified framework, we can harness the power of standardised data to drive better health outcomes and support informed decision-making across Australia noting that maximising our ability to achieve this will require data federation and/or linkage.

5.2.8. Analysis Network

- *Coordination of Multi Centre Studies*: Facilitating collaborative research across institutions.
- *Research Methodology Training*: Offering resources and training to enhance researcher skills.
- *Common Analytics Processes*: Designing shared frameworks and automation tools.
- *Shared Tools, Coding, and Modelling*: Promoting collaboration through common resources.
- *Creation of a Publication and authorship policy*

5.3. Establishment of an Evidence Network Coordinating Node

To implement the OMOP CDM framework successfully across jurisdictions in Australia, we propose the establishment of a Coordinating Node. This initiative will oversee all aspects of the framework development management of contracts and funding to support ongoing projects, fostering sustainability and efficient resource allocation.

While the Coordinating Node will provide oversight, each partner node will maintain autonomy over its implementation processes. They will jointly be responsible for the initiative's success, leveraging local knowledge and trust to tailor strategies that meet their unique needs.

5.3.1. Objectives of the Coordinating Node

- Provide strategic leadership for framework.
- Enhance collaboration and communication among stakeholders.
- Monitor progress and evaluate the impact of OMOP CDM implementation.
- Allocate resources effectively and manage funding for research initiatives.

5.3.2. Key Functions of the Coordinating Node

- *Leadership and Governance*: Establish a governance structure with representatives from government, healthcare providers, academic institutions, and data custodians.
- *Resource Management*: Oversee the allocation of resources for successful OMOP CDM implementation, including financial, technological, and human resources.
- *Sub-Contracts and Research Agreements*: Manage agreements between state nodes to support collaborative research efforts, ensuring alignment with OMOP CDM goals.
- *Communication Facilitation*: Serve as a central hub for communication among all stakeholders involved in OMO CDM implementation.
- *Stakeholder Engagement*: Engage healthcare providers, patient advocacy groups, researchers, and policymakers to consider diverse perspectives.

5.3.3. Proposed Nodes for OMOP CDM Implementation

Each participating state or territory will establish its own node, while a central coordinating node will consist of representatives from all state nodes to ensure cohesive governance and collaboration. These nodes will leverage existing OMOP CDM datasets, expertise, and best practices.

5.4. Assessment of Existing OMOP CDM Datasets

In addition, it would be beneficial to identify if any EMR systems commonly used in Australia have already been converted to OMOP CDM internationally. Leveraging existing OMOP CDM implementations of these systems could significantly expedite our adoption process. For example, Epic has been successfully converted to OMOP CDM at Johns Hopkins Hospital²⁴, and Veradigm (Allscripts) has announced that data from its Veradigm Network EHR will be available in the OMOP CDM format²⁵. This international work provides valuable resources and models for Australian implementation.

As part of the implementation of the OMOP CDM in Australia, an initial and logical step is to build upon the existing OMOP CDM conversions that have already taken place. These prior conversions can be leveraged to facilitate future efforts. For example, lessons learned from the conversion of Epic data at The Royal Children's Hospital Melbourne can inform the conversion of Epic data in the new Single Digital Patient Record (SDPR) initiative in New South Wales.

5.4.1. Resource Allocation and Expansion

Following the gap analysis, additional resources will be allocated to improve existing OMOP CDM datasets, focusing on large-scale implementations within major health systems such as Queensland Health, ACT Health, and SA Health. EMR dataset conversions already funded via previous ARDC work will be supported.

5.4.2. Integration with New Initiatives

The new EPIC implementation within NSW Health will be explored for opportunities to integrate EPIC data into the OMOP CDM framework, ensuring compatibility with OMOP CDM.

5.5. Data Localisation and Security

OMOP CDM databases will leverage existing EMR data locations, maintaining compliance with local data protection regulations. Security measures will be implemented to ensure data integrity and confidentiality while enabling efficient access for analysis.

5.6. Use Cases

Once data governance frameworks and technical conversions are established, the data can be utilised to address questions of state, national and international significance. These

questions may pertain to pharmacovigilance, disease epidemiology, and healthcare operational challenges. Each organisation or jurisdiction can independently design their own research questions or collaborate with others for broader insights.

There are several mechanisms for designing study questions. The OHDSI open-source dashboard, Atlas, allows users to visually explore data and design basic study questions. For more advanced queries, RStudio can connect to the OMOP CDM, enabling custom scripting for complex analyses. Additionally, some groups have integrated third-party commercial tools, such as Power BI for data analysis.

5.7. Network Studies

Network studies in OHDSI refer to collaborative research projects conducted across multiple institutions or organisations, leveraging a distributed data network ²⁶. These studies allow researchers to run analyses on harmonised OMOP CDM data from different sources while maintaining local control over the data, as it stays behind the respective institution's firewall.

Key aspects of Network Studies include:

1. *Distributed Data Network*: Each participating site stores its data in the OMOP CDM format, which allows for standardised queries and analysis across different institutions without moving sensitive data. Analyses are executed locally, and only the aggregated results are shared.
2. *Shared Protocols*: OHDSI network studies rely on shared research protocols. Researchers develop a study design, which is then executed across the network. Each institution can apply the study protocol to its OMOP CDM data, ensuring consistency in the way data is analysed.
3. *Scalability and Collaboration*: By pooling data from multiple sites, OHDSI network studies offer broader population coverage and diverse datasets, leading to more robust and generalisable results. This model fosters collaboration among researchers worldwide, enabling insights into drug safety, disease epidemiology, and healthcare outcomes on a larger scale.
4. *Reproducibility and Transparency*: OHDSI promotes open science principles, meaning that the methods and code for network studies are made available to the wider community. This transparency allows for the reproducibility of findings and encourages cross-validation of results across various settings.
5. *Tools and Technology*: OHDSI provides a suite of tools such as Atlas for study design and execution, and a data quality dashboard for data quality checks. RStudio and Python are often used for advanced scripting and analytics. These tools ensure a flexible, yet standardised, approach to conducting network studies.

5.7.1. The Patient Journey and Record Linkage

Models for disease prevention, risk stratification and outcomes tracking need data across the spectrum of care. Access to pathology test results, diagnoses and prescribing are examples of community-held data that is essential beyond hospital EMR data. In the United States, the health insurer model of care means patients are cared for by a single insurer organisation covering all aspects of their care. In many cases, international network studies rely on cross-sectional information about patients. In Australia, this can only be achieved through record-linkage as we do not have single EMR databases that span all aspects of patient care.

Such linkage is not unprecedented and has been successfully implemented without OMOP conversion in the research activities of the Victorian Comprehensive Cancer Centre, Data Connect Alliance^{27,28}. Their work includes utilising primary care data to investigate early detection and prevention of colorectal cancer, lung cancer and better, earlier diagnoses of rare cancers such as sarcoma/bone and soft tissue cancers. Their work also includes linkage to national death data and disease registries. From a technical perspective, this has been achieved by undertaking record linkage via the Centre for Victorian Data Linkage and the provision of the combined dataset in a Secure Research Environment (CVDL VALT). The trusted nature of the linkage combined with the data access being limited to a Secure Research Environment have been key enablers to the data application process, achieving the requirements and justifications to support a waiver of patient consent model.

In the future, undertaking such research on data converted to the OMOP Common Data Model gives an exciting additional opportunity that further protects the rights of the individual. With OMOP, it is possible to formulate a research question and have it executed on the data by a trusted party. In this manner, in the future it would be possible to create highly restricted linked datasets where the researcher applies to have their question run against the linked dataset without them having any access whatsoever to the underlying data.

This integration framework concentrates on conversion, management and governance of data from hospital EMR's. There is however acknowledgement that hospital EMR databases are often isolated. Indeed, in Victoria a patient may attend multiple hospitals and achieving a holistic view of patient hospitalisation would only be possible by linking hospital datasets or utilising state administrative data.

5.7.2. Future Automated Federated Learning

The code-sharing process in network studies can be further refined in the future. Instead of relying on a human operator to manually share and load code, this process could be automated. Code could be distributed from a central node to partner nodes via an API,

streamlining the workflow. This would accelerate analysis, enable near real-time data processing, and reduce the need for human intervention.

It is important to note that this federated approach would require appropriate governance across the participating node organisations.

A prototype of this type of federated system, “FeederNet”^{29,12}, has been successfully evaluated in South Korea. While still at the cutting edge of network studies, it shows great promise for future research collaborations.

6. Summary

The framework proposed here, centred on the adoption of the OMOP CDM, presents a significant opportunity to transform the Australian healthcare research landscape. By leveraging existing resources, expertise, and infrastructure, and fostering collaboration between stakeholders, Australia can establish an effective and unified system for utilising routinely collected health data.

Through collaborative effort, Australia can unlock the full potential of its healthcare data, enabling researchers to address health challenges, improve patient outcomes, and contribute to a more efficient and effective healthcare system. The insights gained from this standardised data can inform healthcare policies, drive innovation in treatments, and enhance the understanding of disease patterns and population health trends.

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Appendix 1: Landscape Review of EMR's (Hospitals and Primary Care)

Electronic Medical Records (EMR) Systems

This overview includes systems implemented across various healthcare settings in Australia, encompassing general practices, specialist clinics, public and private hospitals, community health centres, and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander health services. The adoption of these systems varies by state, territory, and individual healthcare organisations.

Below is a list of Electronic Medical Records (EMR) systems currently in use in Australia:

Best Practice²⁰

Widely used in general practices across Australia

URL: <https://bpssoftware.net>

Medical Director²⁰ (Owned by Telstra)

One of the most popular EMR systems for general practices

URL: <https://www.medicaldirector.com>

Zedmed²⁰

Used by general practices, especially in Victoria

URL: <https://www.zedmed.com.au>

Sunrise (Allscripts) EMR & PAS³⁰

Sunrise EMR (Electronic Medical Record) is a comprehensive healthcare information system developed by Altera Digital Health (formerly part of Allscripts).

Used in South Australia's public healthcare system

Being rolled out across regional hospitals and local health networks in SA

Cerner⁵ (Oracle Health)

Used in many public hospitals across Australia.

Epic⁵

Implemented in some major hospitals and health networks.

MediRecords³¹

Cloud-based EMR used in primary care, hospitals, and virtual care

Genie Solutions³²

Commonly used by specialists and private practices

Clinic to Cloud³³

Cloud-based practice management and EMR system

Communicare^{34,35} (owned by Telstra)

Widely used in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander health services

TrakCare³⁶

TrakCare is a healthcare information system created by InterSystems that manages and delivers patient care. It offers a unified patient record by integrating clinical, administrative, and financial information.